

NON-EXPLOSIVE METHODOLOGY FOR DYNAMIC BLAST PULSE LOADING OF WIDE AREA COMPOSITE ARMOR PANELS

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1.0 Introduction

Conventional methods for evaluating blast loads on structures require the use of explosives and remote test facilities. Although detonating charges provides the most realistic test conditions for understanding blast effects, non-explosive techniques such as shock tubes and gas guns are popular alternatives to recreate (simulate) blast events in a safe, controlled lab environment [1-3]. Some advantages include repeatable, consistent application of loads, no fire and debris cloud obscuring high speed camera observation, and limited shockwaves which can damage sensors and equipment. Generally, these non-explosive methods test smaller specimens and/or produce limited impulse levels. Wide area target capability is desired in order to investigate the material and global level interactions and to observe damage modes that are not necessarily generated when only testing smaller, coupon-sized specimens. Furthermore, larger (full) scale panels can incorporate important details such as joints and splices, or other connections producing stress concentrations. Therefore, this research project aims to develop a non-explosive methodology for applying representative blast loads onto large-sized (e.g., 610 x 610 mm or greater) flexible composite panels using fast (25 m/s) servo-hydraulic actuators tuned to match the specific impulse of an equivalent explosive charge. To assess panel behavior for armor usage, the transmitted pressure and impulse are key metrics of interest, as well as the final deformation state, extent of damage, and whether the panel was breached. Explicit dynamic finite element analysis (FEA) was used to develop the projectile for the non-explosive test methodology.

2.0 Background and Motivation

A typical free air blast explosion generates the pressure time history shown in Figure 1 [4, 5]. The

high pressure, short duration pulse reaches peak pressure P_{max} almost immediately then decreases to ambient pressure P_{amb} and may continue to decrease (P_{neg}) as the gas cools and the shock wave passes. The integration of the pressure time history curve is referred to as the specific impulse [5]. The positive pressure portion of this curve is the most damaging and is thus the focus of the present research.

Figure 1. Idealized pressure time history for free air explosive blast

Explosive charges of various chemical composition, weight, and standoff distances are often used to achieve different dynamic pressure pulses necessary for investigating blast effects on structures [4]. This has been done by Dharmasena et al. [6, 7] for larger sized, 610 x 610 mm stainless honeycomb and pyramidal lattice sandwich core panels subject to TNT (1–3 kg) and C4 (150 g) explosive charges. Smaller charges can even be used at close distance, such as 20 g TNT at 200 mm standoff to investigate 310 x 310 mm aluminum sandwich panels [8]. In this work, impulse measurements were recorded by a four-cable ballistics pendulum. Measuring the impulses of larger charges, such as 1.0–2.5 kg C4 plastic explosive at 500 mm standoff required a larger pendulum, e.g., 1,400–2,700 kg with 2 m arm, for investigating aluminum foam specimens of up to 700 mm in size [9]. As these examples demonstrate,

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explosives of different charge weights and standoff distances can be used to load the panels of varying sizes with a desired impulse level. This flexibility in creating various threat levels is one of the benefits to using explosives. However, explosives do have several drawbacks including limited visibility of the test specimen response due to the fireball and dust/debris cloud, danger in handling the charges, and difficulty in generating repeatable and identical pressure pulses. This last point is critical for being able to quantitatively compare the relative performance of different armor panel structural configurations or material designs. Due in part to these limitations (among others) researchers often use shock tubes, and to a lesser extent, gas guns, to investigate a structure's response to high pressure-short time duration dynamic impulsive loading events.

A shock tube is a cylindrical tube divided into two sections. The first part is the driver section where compressed gas bursts a membrane or an explosive charge is detonated to generate a high pressure pulse [10]. The second part, the driven section, is where the rapidly expanding gases from the driver section can create a high pressure wave front to impulsively load the specimen located at the exit of the tube [1, 2]. In a similar manner to the non-explosive shock tubes, gas guns rely on a tank of pressurized gas to drive an appropriate projectile to impact the target specimen at high velocity, thereby creating a dynamic loading pulse [11]. For both cases, the loading area is limited by the barrel diameter of the apparatus. Shock tube testing by LeBlanc et al. [1] and Tekalur et al. [2] for example, show composite panels up to 305 mm in span and loaded by a 75 mm diameter shock tube generating up to 8.15 MPa peak pressures. For gas gun tests, D'Mello et al. [12] use a 12.7 mm split Hopkinson bar to examine the dynamic crush response of three and seven cell polycarbonate honeycombs. Radford et al. [3] use aluminum foam projectiles, 28.5 mm in diameter and 50 or 100 mm long, to generate over 100 MPa peak pressures with less than 250 μ s pulse duration. While gas gun tests can create blast-level pressure pulses, the target area is limited by the barrel diameter (e.g., 12.7 or 28.5 mm) and cannot provide the same intensity pressure spread over a wide area approaching one or more meters in size. Large diameter shock tubes do exist, such as the 12 m

wide, semi-circular large shock tube in Gramat, France and the 20 m wide, 11 m tall semi-circular Large Blast and Thermal Simulator (LBTS) in White Sands New Mexico. These use multiple compressed gas drivers that may not generate the same pressure wave characteristics compared to a real blast event and often have reflected waves creating secondary shocks within the decaying portion of the blast wave [1, 13]. The large diameter shock tubes that use explosives in the driver section also exhibit some of the drawbacks associated with actual explosive blast tests.

To summarize, the current methods for generating a dynamic, high specific impulse loading pulse typically cannot simultaneously achieve high repeatability (for direct comparison and ranking of various specimen designs), allow good visibility (for velocity calculation and monitoring damage modes), and apply a wide area pressure pulse (to investigate global effects of large structures). Figure 2 provides a qualitative summary of the benefits and limitations of the various current methods, with envelope boundaries residing nearer the radar plot's outer perimeter indicating better performance in each category. For example, an explosive charge has excellent wide area pressure pulse magnitude and short blast duration, but the lowest ranking in visibility, safety, and repeatability/controllability. The Blast Simulator mentioned in Figure 2 is the method discussed in this paper.

Figure 2. Radar plot comparison of dynamic pressure pulse generation methods; outer radius indicates better characteristics

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The UC San Diego Blast Simulator facility has the unique capability to create the wide area-high magnitude pressure pulses, up to 84,000 Pa*s, necessary to test large-sized panels without the use of explosives. It has high repeatability and controllability, short pulse durations, good visibility during the entire event duration, and relatively safe operation. The system uses fast servo-hydraulic actuators to launch a projectile package (as shown in Figure 3) at a desired velocity in order to apply an impulsive dynamic loading pulse onto targets of interest.

Figure 3. Projectile impact pulse loading concept

The actuators can also be setup drive into the target and pull back [14]. Two actuator types can be selected to provide different capabilities (25 m/s and 50 m/s available) and can be configured as a single unit or part of a multiple unit array. The latter configuration enables either simultaneous operation to launch heavier masses, or staged to impact different portions of the structure at different time intervals [15] to represent the arrival of a non-planar blast front. This allows large sized (1–3 m) structures to now be tested with some of the same features (e.g., impulse level, pulse duration, staged impact times) traditionally available only to the explosive-based methods. It should be noted that despite the use of the high speed actuators, the velocities and peak pressures created are still typically lower than the shockwave propagation velocity and peak pressures created by an actual close-in explosive detonation. Also, only the positive portion of the pressure time history curve (Figure 1) can be represented. However, based on specific impulse matching, the total area under the

pressure time history curve for both actual explosive and non-explosive methods can be made equal, and thus a short-duration, high peak pressure blast pulse of an explosive charge can be represented by a longer-time duration but lower peak pressure pulse generated by the Blast Simulator (see Figure 4). Specific impulse matching has been shown to produce damage on concrete columns comparable to that produced by real explosives [5].

Figure 4. Impulse matching showing identical specific impulse but different peak pressures and time durations

Thus, the proposed non-explosive, wide area panel tests will: (i) investigate the use of the Blast Simulator and tuned projectile package to generate a 7,520 Pa*s specific impulse which is typical of a close-in explosive detonation of approximately 1.74 kg TNT at 305 mm standoff, (ii) assess and compare the damage modes and extent of damage between non-explosive and actual blast tests, and (iii) compare the performance of sandwich panel designs relative to a steel panel baseline.

3.0 Test Setup

3.1 Overview

For testing 610 x 610 mm armor panels, the Blast Simulator was configured with a single 25 m/s actuator. An aluminum pusher plate was attached to the end of the actuator ram and interfaced with the projectile through a central locating shaft. On triggering, a poppet valve opened and high pressure (34 MPa) hydraulic fluid accelerated the ram and 50.3 kg projectile to a velocity of 24.6 m/s, and then decelerated to prevent it from striking the specimen. The projectile separated from the pusher plate at the beginning of the deceleration phase and began free

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flight at 24.6 m/s constant velocity for approximately 240 mm before impacting the panel (see Figure 3 for overview of the system and Figure 5 for high speed camera capture of projectile flight and impact). On the back face of the panel was placed a 13.7 kg aluminum transmission plate, with the same cross sectional dimensions as the projectile (406 x 406 mm). The transmission plate rested on low friction guides and was attached to the backside of the panel with a small quantity of grease (see Figure 6). On impact, the transmission plate would be accelerated at the same rate as the panel back surface before being released and entering free flight at a constant velocity matching the peak velocity the test panel achieved prior to decelerating. A shock accelerometer at the center of gravity of the transmission plate was used for velocity and momentum calculations of the plate (transmitted impulse) and provided indirect measurement of transmitted pressure via $F = \text{mass} \times \text{acceleration} = \text{pressure} \times \text{area}$ relationship. The concept for the transmission plate was based on existing actual blast test methodology used by industry.

The window fixture supporting the panels was fabricated from 4130 chromoly steel, dimensions 610 x 610 x 12.7 mm, with a 483 x 483 mm opening. Twenty equal-spaced 12.7 mm diameter holes were located around the window opening at 533 x 533 mm distance to bolt the window fixture and panel together for testing. The window fixture and steel support legs were mounted horizontally (panel facing horizontal) to a post-tensioned 9,000 kg concrete block.

Actual explosive based tests were conducted by Oregon Ballistics Laboratory using the same test fixture mounted vertically (panel facing downward). A 1.37 kg charge of C4 (equivalent to 1.74 kg TNT) was placed underneath the panel at 305 mm standoff and detonated (see Figure 7). The transmission plate, placed on the backside of the panel, was launched due to the panel's deformation. For the blast tests, panel velocities were calculated from the "hang time" of the plate (time between detonation and when plate fell to the ground) as both high speed video and accelerometer data were often unusable.

Figure 5. Test NE_CFM_A2 showing impact sequence (from top) projectile acceleration, release, impact, and transmission plate motion

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Figure 6. Transmission plate viewed from front of test fixture with panel removed (left) and through high speed camera window (right)

Figure 7. Actual blast test setup showing charge (on ground) and test specimen surface at 305 mm above charge

3.2 Projectile Development

A critical aspect of the non-explosive methodology was the design of the projectile. It was desired that the projectile: (i) impart a wide area pressure load, (ii) have spatial and temporal variations representing a close-in blast, such that the center of the projectile arrived sooner and with higher impulse than the outermost positions, and (iii) minimize ringing (which can arise from metal to metal contact), double hits, and permit some misalignment of the projectile in case the free flight was not perfectly straight. To assist in the projectile development, finite element analysis (FEA) with Abaqus/Explicit was used to analyze a quarter symmetric model of the entire system, including projectile package, test specimen in fixture, and transmission plate. In this model, the target panel was rolled homogeneous armor (RHA) steel, chosen due to its well-known material behavior. The 6.35 mm thick RHA panel was modeled with shell elements initially for the

projectile proof of concept and later with four layers of solid elements. Both the projectile and aluminum transmission plate were modeled with solid elements while the test fixture used shells. Symmetry boundary conditions (BCs) were enforced for all sections at the symmetry faces, fixed BCs were assigned at the base of the support fixture, and tie constraints were defined for the fixture to specimen interfaces at the same location as the physical bolted connections. Further details of this model and validation with the physical tests were not included herein for reasons of brevity.

To create the wide area pressure load (as opposed to a smaller concentrated-area) on the large-sized flexible panels, it was necessary to allow the projectile to deform. Launching a 406 x 406 mm one-piece solid block projectile would provide a uniform load only upon initial contact with the panel, but once the panel started to deform, the solid projectile would produce high stresses in localized regions around the boundaries and corners of the projectile (as shown by the FEA-predicted, quarter-symmetric, contact pressures in Figure 8). This type of loading would not be an accurate representation of a close-in blast profile which would have concentrated pressures at the panel center, and not at the periphery.

Figure 8. Quarter-symmetric FEA results showing contact pressure due to a solid 406 x 406 mm projectile localized around the projectile periphery

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Thus, the tiled array projectile concept was devised, where each individual block in the projectile package could rotate or translate independent of one another and conform to the deforming flexible target panel. This geometry would provide a more uniform pressure distribution representative of a blast load, which is shown by the FEA-predicted, quarter symmetric model in Figure 9. The contact pressures produced by a 25-tile array projectile package were more evenly distributed and not concentrated around the panel periphery as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 9. Quarter-symmetric FEA results showing more uniform contact pressure on the panel surface due to 406 x 406 mm tiled projectile

Spatial variations in impulse loading were achieved by varying the individual masses within the 25 block projectile package. The composition of each block was chosen as a combination of steel and aluminum, as shown in Figure 10, since impulse can only be adjusted by mass if all blocks had the same velocity. Each block in the projectile was designated by letter A to F, with blocks B and C being identical and blocks D and E being identical (see Figure 10). For the center tile block F applying 100% level specific impulse, then each outward ring of blocks would theoretically apply 97% (D, E), 89% (B, C), and 72% (A) of block F's impulse. This idealized spatial variation in specific impulse is shown in Figure 11, with the labeled blocks A-F shown in the second quadrant. In reality, the center block F had a lower

mass than blocks D/E due to a required pocket for mounting the projectile to the pusher shaft. Mass of the center block F was 2.09 kg, blocks D/E were 2.15 kg, blocks B/C were 1.92 kg and block A was 1.54 kg.

Figure 10. Block details of tiled projectile package

Figure 11. Idealized specific impulse intensity mapped onto panel surface at locations A-F

Temporal variations in pressure pulse arrival times were achieved by offsetting the height of the central blocks in a concentric manner. The center (F) was spaced +3.18 mm, the next ring (D/E) was +1.59 mm, and the others (A, B/C) were set at 0 mm. For the arrival velocity of 24.6 m/s, this would theoretically create a 0.13 ms delay in arrival time,

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loading the center portion of the panel first, thus reflecting the temporal-spatial distribution which would be produced by a close-in blast at 305 mm standoff.

Finally, on the face of each block was mounted a tuned foam pulse shaper. The 160 kg/m^3 -density, tetrahedral shaped foam served to: reduce the likelihood of ringing due to metal-to-metal contact, engage the panel on impact in a manner that maintained contact and eliminated double hits, and allow for slight misalignment of the projectile upon impact after its short free flight.

The finalized projectile array configuration was the 25 block (5x5) tiled projectile shown Figure 12. The overall coverage of the tile array was 406 x 406 mm, with a 6.35 mm gap between each of the blocks. Each block had planar dimensions 76 x 76 mm and thicknesses ranging from 50.8 to 54.0 mm.

Figure 12. 5x5 tiled array projectile package assembled and mounted to pusher plate

The blocks were attached via single bolt to a thin 3.18 mm aluminum sheet that was notched at each attachment point to allow the blocks to move freely during the impact (see the “+” cutouts on the bolt holes in Figure 10). The aluminum sheet also facilitated handling the 50.3 kg projectile package

and enabled the entire 5x5 array to be supported at only one point: the center block which was at the projectile’s center of gravity (CG). The center steel block was bored to accept a lubricated bronze sleeve bushing which slipped over the 25.4 mm diameter pusher plate shaft. This arrangement was found to permit a clean release of the tile array, maintaining planar and vertical orientation during its (short) free flight prior to impacting the target panel (see Figure 5).

3.3 Test Specimens

Ten different panel designs, 27 total including replicates, were tested with the non-explosive Blast Simulator (NE test series). Five panels (no replicates) were tested with actual explosives by Oregon Ballistics Laboratory (BL test series). The majority of panel designs used a sandwich construction, e.g., composite front face and aluminum foam core (CFM) or composite front face and double stainless steel honeycomb core (CDH). Variations of these designs were designated A, B, C, and so forth, and individual (replicate) panels were identified numerically, e.g., NE_CDH_A1 refers to the non-explosive test, composite/double honeycomb panel, variant A, first panel. Solid, 6.35 mm thick RHA steel served as a baseline reference. Additional constructions include aluminum face/aluminum foam core (AFM), composite/single honeycomb core (CSH), composite/double nanocrystalline foam core (CDN), and an aluminum panel (ALUM). Only three panel designs CFM_A, CDH_A, and RHA were tested by both non-explosive and actual blast tests. Representative core specimens are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Armor panel cross-sections

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4.0 Test Results

4.1 Impulse Comparison

The Blast Simulator was used to apply an impulse of 1,240 N*s or 7,520 Pa*s over 406 x 406 mm area with a standard deviation of 12 N*s (1 %) for all 27 tests. The actual blast tests applied an assumed 1,956 N*s, equal to 8,400 Pa*s over 483 x 483 mm (the loading area was not limited to the same 406 x 406 mm area as the projectile). The applied and transmitted impulses are summarized for the non-explosive methodology in Table 1 and the actual blast tests in Table 2.

Table 1. Non-explosive (NE) impulse levels

Specimen ID	Areal Density (kg/m ²)	Impulse		
		Flyer (N*s)	Transm. (N*s)	(F-T)/F (%)
NE_CFM_A1	33.64	1,252	256	79.6
NE_CFM_A2	34.62	1,212	272	77.5
NE_CFM_A3	33.07	1,243	286	77.0
NE_CDH_A1	27.07	1,253	313	75.0
NE_CDH_A2	27.10	1,214	309	74.5
NE_CDH_A3	27.09	1,254	297	76.3
NE_CFM_B1	32.75	1,241	293	76.4
NE_CFM_B2	31.75	1,240	279	77.5
NE_CFM_B3	32.87	1,258	292	76.8
NE_CFM_C1	27.55	1,235	274	77.8
NE_CFM_C2	30.09	1,248	306	75.5
NE_CFM_C3	27.38	1,235	288	76.7
NE_CFM_D1	31.77	1,232	256	79.2
NE_CFM_D2	30.89	1,249	286	77.1
NE_CFM_D3	31.83	1,231	285	76.9
NE_CDH_B1	25.91	1,244	303	75.6
NE_CDH_B2	25.91	1,252	299	76.1
NE_CDH_B3	25.83	1,231	299	75.7
NE_CDH_C1	25.21	1,251	308	75.3
NE_CDH_C2	25.25	1,224	290	76.3
NE_CDH_C3	25.33	1,231	298	75.8
NE_CDN_A1	24.62	1,229	314	74.4
NE_CDN_A2	24.68	1,246	332	73.4
NE_ALUM	25.72	1,230	295	76.0
NE_RHA_01	48.82	1,242	308	75.2
NE_RHA_02	48.82	1,255	310	75.3
NE_RHA_03	48.82	1,245	299	76.0

Table 2. Actual blast (BL) impulse levels

Specimen ID	Impulse		
	Blast (N*s)	Transm. (N*s)	(F-T)/F (%)
BL_CSH_A1	1,956	592	69.7
BL_AFM_A1	1,956	366	81.3
BL_CFM_A4	1,956	384	80.4
BL_CDH_A4	1,956	403	79.4
BL_RHA_04	1,956	363	81.5

The impulse absorption percentage (last columns in Tables 1 and 2) is calculated by subtracting the impulse of the transmission plate from the applied impulse level, and dividing by the applied impulse. It is found to be nearly constant for all panels tested by both non-explosive Blast Simulator and actual explosive tests regardless of panel construction. This result is expected as impulse tends to be conserved, regardless of what non-linear processes the panel might undergo during its dynamic response. Thus the impulse absorption is not a discriminating metric for comparing panel performance, but rather, is an indicator of how consistently the loading was applied and the how the transmission plate responded within and across test methods. For the explosive blast test, the charge was designed to provide 8,400 Pa*s, but there was no assurance that this level of specific impulse was actually applied to the panel surface. Also, the first blast test, BL_CSH_A1, used a slightly different test configuration, both closer to the ground and with more lateral obstructions for the expanding gases. It was possible that this configuration may have amplified the pressure pulse as this panel showed the highest transmission plate velocity that was not replicated in any other test and caused damage to the test fixture (which was repaired and reconfigured as shown in Figure 7 for the remaining four BL tests). However, data confirming higher pressures were not available so this test (and all BL tests) was assumed to apply 1,956 N*s to the panel surface.

4.2 Transmitted Acceleration Comparison

Examining the accelerometer data for the transmission plate tested by the Blast Simulator shows significant reductions in transmitted accelerations for the sandwich specimens compared to the RHA baseline. This implies that the transmitted pressures are reduced by the same

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amount, considering that acceleration scales directly with force, and for a constant area, also scales directly with pressure (i.e., $F = \text{pressure} \times \text{area} = \text{mass} \times \text{acceleration}$). The transmitted pressure is a key metric of interest in comparing vehicle armored panels since it can cause injury to personnel. Two components of transmitted pressure are considered here, initial-average and maximum. The initial-average pressure is proportional to the acceleration of the transmission plate when it is directly in contact with the panel prior to free flight. It is calculated as the average of the acceleration over an initial period of time while the panel and transmission plate are still in contact. An example of typical data is shown in Figure 14. Within that same time period, a maximum acceleration is also measured, shown by the black square symbol in Figure 14. Initial-average and peak accelerations are summarized in Table 3 for the non-explosive tests. The sandwich panels show initial-average acceleration reductions of up to 38.8% compared to the RHA steel and peak acceleration reductions of up to 75.9%, although NE_CDN_A did show a higher initial-average acceleration of 38.9% compared to RHA. The reduction in acceleration can be attributed to the sandwich core material, which crushed to absorb some of the impulsive load and attenuated the propagation of the shockwave through the material.

Figure 14. Transmission plate acceleration time history for NE_CDH_A2

Table 3. Non-explosive (NE) transmission plate accelerations (pressures) and reduction w.r.t. RHA

Specimen Series	Init-Avg Accel. (g)	Reduc. Init-Avg w.r.t RHA (%)	Max Accel. (g)	Reduc. Max w.r.t. RHA (%)
CFM_A	2,190	35.5	5,320	62.9
CDH_A	2,310	31.8	3,970	72.4
CFM_B	2,330	31.2	5,740	60.0
CFM_C	2,250	33.7	5,300	63.1
CDH_D	2,780	18.1	4,760	66.8
CDH_B	2,150	36.6	3,470	75.9
CDH_C	2,330	31.2	4,410	69.3
CDN_A	4,710	-38.9	6,800	52.7
ALUM	2,070	38.8	7,920	44.8
RHA	3,390	0.0	14,400	0.0

For the BL test series, the data cables were often damaged prior to reaching peak acceleration and thus neither initial nor peak acceleration could be measured. The available data does indicate that the sandwich panels may have mitigated the transmitted acceleration compared to RHA due to slope of the acceleration vs. time curves and the apparent onset of a maximum value for BL_AFM_A1 and BL_CFM_A4, along with a maximum for BL_CSH_A1 (see Figure 15). Conclusive answers would require additional blast testing with higher-rated shock sensors as the accelerations appear to be an order of magnitude higher than the NE test series.

Figure 15. Transmission plate acceleration time history for BL tests (BL_CDH_A4 data not available)

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4.3 Internal Damage Comparison

The sandwich panels tested with actual explosives developed a higher level of internal damage compared to the non-explosive test method (e.g., see center-cut sectioned foam core panels in Figures 16 and 17 subjected to non-explosive loading and actual blast, respectively, and the double honeycomb panels in Figures 18 and 19). For the non-explosive tests, the internal core structures of the sandwich panels were largely intact and almost undamaged, especially at the panel center. Damage was sustained primarily around the clamped boundaries of the window fixture. In the case of the CFM panels, front layer separation from the core due to large deformations and weak bonding also occurred. The blast tests showed similar damage modes as the NE tests, but more extensive. This may be due in part to the explosive detonation applying a more dynamic pressure pulse to the panel front surface thereby causing a mismatch in the speed of deformation between the panel's front and back surfaces. The mismatch was worsened by the inertia effects of the transmission mass being located on the back surface. The RHA panel, which did not use a sandwich core configuration, did not have visible internal damage to assess differences between test methods. For both test methods, no panel of any construction type was breached.

Figure 16. Panel NE_CFM_A2 showing intact core at panel center (top) and shear damage at clamped boundary (bottom) with front face separation

Figure 17. Panel BL_CFM_A4 showing deformed profile and extensive core crush (top) and shear damage at clamped boundary (bottom) with front face separation

Figure 18. Panel NE_CDH_A1 showing deformed profile and generally intact core throughout (top) and core crush at clamped boundary (bottom)

Figure 19. Panel BL_CDH_A1 extensively damaged (top) and core crush at clamped boundary (bottom)

4.4 Deformation Profile Comparison

The post-test permanent deformation profiles measured along the panel centerline are shown in Figures 20 to 22 for CFM_A, CDH_A, and RHA panel types. Panel type CFM_A had larger permanent deformations than panel type CDH_A which in turn, had higher permanent deformation than RHA. Sandwich panel variations of the CFM and CDH core had similar profiles. The non-explosive profiles were much more symmetric about the centerline compared to the BL test series (see Figure 20), and replicate tests of a given panel type show overlaying profiles, indicating both the consistency of panel construction and the repeatability of the NE methodology, especially in Figure 21. The blast tests did not uniformly load the panels in some instances (e.g., BL_CFM_A1 in Figure 20 shows a skewed deformation profile). The back face deformation profile may provide a more accurate representation of the final deformed shape still since it represents the limit of the facesheet plastic deformation during impact. The front facesheet in some instances was later found to have separated from the core due to the polymer layer tearing (see Figure 20, front layer of NE_CFM_A1 is closer to the back face and specimens A2 and A3 are further away).

Figure 20. Deformation profiles for CFM_A

Figure 21. Deformation profiles for CDH_A

Figure 22. Deformation profiles for RHA

5.0 Conclusions

Generating a non-explosive, wide area, spatially and temporally varying dynamic pressure pulse was achieved by impact forces created by a segmented array projectile package. The system created a 7,520 Pa*s specific impulse, applied over a 406 x 406 mm area, which was used to represent the specific impulse of a 1.74 kg charge of TNT at 305 mm standoff distance. The dynamic pressure loading was very consistent with a 1% standard deviation in applied impulse for the 27 tests. This consistency of loading was necessary for comparing various armor panel designs with respect to transmitted pressure, impulse attenuation, and extent of damage. The transmitted impulse attenuation was found to be similar between all panels and both the non-explosive method (mean 76.3%) and the actual blast

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tests (mean 78.6%) showed equivalent measurements. Transmitted pressures for the non-explosive methodology were measured indirectly via transmitted accelerations of a transmission plate. The non-explosive test methodology showed sandwich panel constructions attenuated initial-average and peak transmitted acceleration (i.e., pressures) by up to 36.6% and 75.9%, respectively, compared to conventional RHA steel armored plate. Different panel constructions had different pressure attenuations, depending on the facesheet and core design. Deformation profiles for both actual blast and non-explosive tests were similar for a given panel design, but the non-explosive methodology applied a much more symmetric (as assessed by the deformation profile), consistent, and repeatable loading. Internal damage modes for the sandwich panels were similar for both methods, but more extensive core crushing occurred for the actual blast tests. The RHA steel plate, which did not use a sandwich construction, appeared to have similar deformation profiles and extent of damage for both blast and non-explosive tests. Thus, the non-explosive methodology has been shown to be able to generate a wide area, dynamic pressure pulse loading with a similar specific impulse as an equivalent explosive-based test, while also maintaining the repeatability, visibility, and consistency of a lab-controlled environment that is necessary for comparing the relative performance of different armored panel designs.

6.0 Acknowledgements

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7.0 References

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